

CORRUPTION AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

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Abstract

Background: Environmental protection is an important segment of societal life, both nationally and internationally. Especially in conditions of climate change, environmental crimes and sustainable development, environmental protection is very important to create safe conditions for all living beings.

Environmental protection is directly related to the activities of the competent state bodies, but also of other institutions in the field. This includes many activities aimed at environmental protection, and activities to combat environmental crimes are especially important.

Within these activities, the presence of corruption in the field of environmental protection is notable, and hence the need to study anti-corruption measures in this area. Certain analyses in the Republic of North Macedonia indicate that corruption in the field of combating environmental crimes is significant, and there are examples of bribery of officials responsible for environmental protection.

Methods: These phenomena will be analysed with the method of content analysis. The author of the text explores these phenomena, with the aim to analyse and propose measures to combat corruption in the field of environmental protection in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Results: According to SOCTA and other research, corruption is directly related to environmental crimes in our country.

Conclusion: We need anti-corruption measures for combating environmental crimes without corruption.

Key words: corruption, environmental crimes etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a serious social problem that affects all spheres of social life. In the Republic of North Macedonia, this problem is most often represented as a criminal offence that is associated with receiving and giving bribes. There are numerous forms of committing these punishable behaviours, and numerous professions are represented, including: doctors, professors, police officers, customs officers, members of political parties, and many others. Although there are a certain number of institutions whose main activity, among others, is the suppression of this type of crime, this phenomenon is still on the rise.

According to certain research by the Faculty of Security in 2016 regarding bribery, 20.45% of the total number of respondents stated that they were exposed to the risk of corruption and gave a bribe, 60.86% stated that they were not in a position to give a bribe, and a part of the respondents – 18.69% did not want to state their opinion. It can be

concluded that a quarter of the total number of respondents gave a bribe (Mojanoski, Mališ Sazdovska, Nikolovski et al. 2016).

To monitor the current situation regarding corruption in the country, a special European Union Report is being prepared for the Republic of North Macedonia, so the Report for 2023 states that “The country is in between some and moderate level of preparation in preventing and fighting corruption. No progress has been made. Corruption remains widespread in many areas and this issue is of concern. The number of delays and reversals of trials in high-level corruption cases has increased, resulting in some cases with the statute of limitations expiring. The Criminal Code was amended following an accelerated parliamentary procedure. The maximum statutory penalty for specific corruption-related crimes was reduced, which had implications for the application of the statute of limitations and affected, halting or even terminating many high-level corruption cases, including those by the former Special Public Prosecutor's Office (SPO). The amendments also hinder the ability of the authorities to investigate and prosecute such crimes. This issue raises serious concerns”.

Based on the statements in the Report, it can be concluded that the country still faces major challenges in the field of anti-corruption measures and activities that need to be undertaken to suppress this negative social phenomenon.

The competent authorities for combating corruption are:

- The Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, which has developed an Action 21 plan to combat corruption. In August 2017, the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia also adopted a decision to adopt a Strategy for Strengthening the Capacities for Conducting Financial Investigations and Confiscation of Property with an Action Plan for its implementation in the period from 2018 to 2020.

- The Parliament of the Republic of North Macedonia adopts a national strategy, reviews and adopts reports from the SCPC, and adopts a budget for the SCPC.

- Ministry of Finance, SCPC submits a budget proposal to the ministry,

- Public prosecutor's offices and courts, processing criminal offences related to corruption and conflict of interest,

- State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, is autonomous and independent in the performance of its duties and has the status of a legal entity. The Commission adopts a national strategy with an action plan, conducts anti-corruption inspections of laws and other acts, acts on reports, initiates initiatives, monitors the legality of operations, etc. The Commission submits a report to the Parliament, but also to the President of the Republic of Macedonia, the Government of the Republic of Macedonia and the media.

The State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) has a legal obligation to adopt a five-year National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest with an action plan for its implementation. This is the first document in the field of combating corruption to be adopted at the highest level, i.e. by the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia.

- Local self-government, municipalities adopt an Annual Plan for the Fight against Corruption and Conflict of Interest and an action plan for identified measures with activities and indicators.

- Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning,

- State Inspectorate for Environment, cooperation with the business community, civil society associations, educational and scientific institutions and all stakeholders who can contribute with their activities to increase transparency, and emphasized cooperation with

the SCPC for the prevention of corruption in the area of transparency and integrity of the inspection service (Malish Szdovska, 2024).

In addition to these competent state and local government bodies, the Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Justice, Customs Administration, Financial Police, Inspection Council, Financial Intelligence Administration, Public Revenue Office, etc. have the competence and authority to act in the area of combating corruption.

The Basic Public Prosecutor's Office for Prosecution of Organized Crime and Corruption is responsible for the most complex forms of organized crime and high-level corruption and is responsible for handling cases related to organized crime and corruption throughout the territory of the Republic of North Macedonia. The Basic Public Prosecutor's Office for Prosecution of Organized Crime and Corruption is located in Skopje. It is accountable for its work to the Public Prosecutor of the Republic of North Macedonia, who supervises the work of this prosecutor's office, as well as to the Council of Public Prosecutors. The key guarantee for its functioning in accordance with the law is financial independence, which is the basic pillar and prerequisite for the independence of every institution, including the Public Prosecutor's Office.

Several competent authorities are responsible for financial investigations into environmental crimes related to giving and receiving bribes, among which the Financial Police, the Financial Intelligence Unit and the Public Revenue Office play a key role (Malish Szdovska, 2025).

2. Corruption and environmental protection

In addition to other areas in which corruption is evident, it can be concluded that there is also a serious presence of corruption in the area of environmental protection. According to the Serious and Organized Crime Threat Assessment 2021 (SOCTA, 2021) prepared by the Bureau of Public Security under the Ministry of Interior, it is concluded for environmental crimes that the number of detected crimes does not reflect the real situation, and in cases of environmental endangerment there are situations that are not fully documented and do not have a criminal-legal conclusion. The lack of the detection function of the competent authorities, which have difficulty recognizing crimes, is also highlighted as a problem. Forest devastation is a crime that, in its manifestations, in most cases represents organized crime. Illegal logging in the Republic of Macedonia is characterized as "highly threatening, with a large dark number, without indications of stopping criminal activity". Illegal logging and deforestation are directly linked to corruption, which is often used to facilitate the commission of these crimes (SOCTA, 2021).

Based on the results of SOCTA, corrupt abuse has been observed among:

- Employees of the Real Estate Cadastre Agency who carry out unfounded changes in the ownership of forest plots, from state ownership to private ownership of individuals, based on which logging permits are later issued,
- Employees of the PE National Forests for abuses in checking timber and issuing consignment notes for transport and sale,
- Employees of the Police and Forest Police for evading control by giving bribes.

Analysing the conclusions of the Assessment, it can be concluded that "corruption is a key driver of environmental crime, and it significantly affects the detection activity, which is why it is assumed that organized forms are not fully detected" (SOCTA, 2021).

The Serious and Organized Crime Threat Assessment, Mid-Term Review 2023, states that “environmental crime has increased by 26.3% compared to the previous period, with the increase being most pronounced in the threat to the environment and nature with waste, for which criminal acts have increased by 327.3%. In this Assessment, as in the previous one, the detection function is assessed as low and does not reflect the real situation on the ground” (SOCTA, 2023). The Assessment states that "environmental crime continues to be a current threat through the illegal use of natural resources, including the threat to the environment and nature with waste, which is increasing. Environmental crime is closely linked with the legal business sector, with criminal structures in the area managing to abuse legal loopholes and use legislative changes for new criminal activity. Also, in the concluding observations, it is concluded that environmental crime is often committed with elements of corruption and informal association of people, the possibility of organized action and cooperation with groups operating in the field of corruption and economic crime is assumed” (SOCTA, 2023).

Another document indicating the existence of corrupt activities in the field of the environment is the Annual Report on the Implementation of the Measures of the National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, planned for implementation in 2021. The Report states that, "The environmental sector in the context of this Strategy consists of public institutions that are part of the central and local government, and with jurisdiction over issues in the field of environmental protection. This sector has gained importance in recent years due to the introduction of various environmental and other permits that business entities need to have in order to be able to start/carry out their operational activities (Annual Report, 2022).

The Report of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, however, states that the commission acted in only 5 cases in the field of the environment during 2022, and that after receiving reports, and in no case on its own initiative.

2.1. Analysis of cases of environmental corruption

In the Republic of North Macedonia, there are several cases of bribery and corruption of persons in the field of ecology, i.e. environmental and nature protection (Analysis Florozon, 2024).

The Financial Police Directorate has filed a criminal complaint against a natural person in the capacity of an official - a Senior Civil Servant at the Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning of the Republic of North Macedonia. The criminal complaint was filed due to the existence of a reasonable suspicion that during 2021 he abused his official position, i.e. acted contrary to Article 108, paragraph 1 and paragraph 8 of the Law on Environment, in such a way that, without inspecting the installation and its operation to determine the fulfilment of the requirements in accordance with legal regulations, he personally prepared and approved an A-integrated environmental permit for JPDKO Drisla Skopje, although they did not possess appropriate equipment and installations.

With the operation "Penta" in December 2014, the commander of the Police Station for Border Surveillance on Lake Ohrid was deprived of his liberty, due to the existence of a well-founded suspicion of committing the crime of Abuse of Official Position and Authority. In addition to the criminal charges against the commander, criminal charges were also filed against four individuals from Struga for committing crimes of "incitement" and "illegal fishing" under the Criminal Code. In this case, it is a senior manager in the Ministry of Internal Affairs who, for a long period of time, organized

a group that illegally caught fish and sold them to restaurants and other catering facilities and private individuals.

The nature of the crime consisted in the activities of the commander, who, in order to gain unlawful material benefit, enabled the other individuals charged to continuously commit the crime of Illegal Fishing in the waters of Lake Ohrid. The commander had to, but failed to, perform official actions in accordance with the legal regulations and did not take measures to carry out control in the waters of Lake Ohrid. He informed the other reported persons about the time and place of the police controls of the lake police, to avoid patrols, placing the nets in places where the lake police would not patrol, in order not to be discovered and not to have the equipment and nets with which they committed the crime of Illegal fishing confiscated. In return for this "service", the commander received monetary compensation or illegally caught fish.

The next case is the example of an employee of the Forest Police in Demir Hisar for accepting a bribe. The employee of the Forest Police from Demir Hisar was deprived of his liberty and suspected of committing a crime under Article 357 of the Criminal Code "accepting a bribe". The employee demanded money in return for not acting, that is, not sanctioning illegal operations. However, the person reported the case to the SVR Bitola and was given forensically processed money, which he gave to the employee of the Forest Police. After handing over the money, the person was deprived of his liberty and 18,000 denars were found on him, which originated from the crime, after which he was detained at the Bitola police station and criminal charges were filed against him.

In 2021, criminal charges were also filed against a state environmental inspector for accepting a bribe, after he received a bribe of 200 euros. He requested and received this money from the owner in Kičevo, and he also had an accomplice who will be prosecuted. The owner had a car lot, and the inspector for the return of the bribe was not supposed to inspect the lot. The criminal complaint was filed due to reasonable suspicion that the state environmental inspector committed a criminal offence of accepting a bribe, while performing his official duty. A criminal complaint was filed against the second defendant for reasonable suspicion of committing a criminal offence of aiding, because he enabled the inspector to take the money from the bribe in the premises of his office in Kičevo.

This occurrence of achieving material benefit from concealing legal violations by polluters was condemned by the State Inspectorate for Environmental Protection.

3. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the above-mentioned cases of corruption in the field of the environment, it can be concluded that there is no effective action to suppress this phenomenon. Namely, there are numerous cases that confirm that employees in various institutions, at various levels of work from the lowest to the highest management positions, undertake corrupt actions and appear as perpetrators of crimes such as accepting a bribe, abuse of official position and authority, etc.

Hence, it can be concluded that this crime is prevalent in the field of the environment and that additional measures and activities are needed for preventive and repressive action in suppressing the crime.

The directions that can be proposed to improve the situation are: efficient criminal investigations into these crimes, increasing awareness among the population about reporting, strengthening the human and technical capacities of the competent authorities

under whose jurisdiction and authority this type of crime is, and perhaps the most important segment is strengthening the integrity of employees in these institutions.

In addition to the above measures, the following activities can be undertaken to prevent corruption, namely:

- strengthening of supervisory and control mechanisms,
- improving the standard and material well-being of the population,
- strengthening of the human and technical capacities of the competent authorities for the suppression of corruption,
- existence of an efficient judicial system and effective rule of law,
- introduction of digitalized procedures,
- education, training and strengthening of the integrity of employees in the competent authorities.

If these anti-corruption measures are implemented in the coming period, we can expect a reduction in the trend of corruption, as well as the creation of conditions for a society in which corruption will be reduced to the lowest level or we will have a state of zero corruption.

4. REFERENCES

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